

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Review Article****PREVENTING BREAST CANCER-A REVIEW ARTICLE**Fateme parooei¹, Mahmood Anbari², Morteza Salarzaei^{1*}, Ali jafari khalilabadi³¹Medical Student, Student Research Committee, Zabol University of Medical Sciences, Zabol, Iran²Zabol University of Medical Sciences, Zabol, Iran³Medical student, Student Research Committee, zahedan University of Medical Sciences, Zahedan, Iran**Abstract:**

Introduction: World Health Organization in 2011, cancer in Iran was reported to be 12% widespread and was recognized as the third most common cause of death. Gastric cancer, breast cancer, and colorectal cancer are the three common cancers in Iran respectively. Breast cancer is the first place cancer widespread among women. The average age of breast cancer diagnosis in the Western countries is 56 years and in Iran 45 years. New developments in the patients care with breast cancer have increased the overall survival rate of the patients in recent years. This increase in survival has doubled the importance of predictive factors of local recurrence and distant metastases of the disease.

Methods: In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify the Preventing Breast cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that was conducted to study the relationship between the Preventing Breast cancers were selected.

Results: American Cancer Association no longer recommends doing monthly BSE, and specialists believe that BSE has the minimum effect in diagnosing breast cancer. Breast masses are not necessarily abnormal, and for women who have menstrual cycle, breast masses appear and disappear.

Discussion and conclusion: This technology makes it possible to see the internal structures of the breast. American Cancer Association suggests that women reaching the age of 40 have an annual mammography. Initial prevention in the form of changes in lifestyle, avoiding risk factors, and education and informing people through mass media like radio, TV, and newspapers in order to increase people's awareness of methods of breast cancer screening is suggested.

Key words: Preventing, Breast cancer

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Please cite this article in press as Morteza Salarzaei *et al*, **Preventing Breast Cancer-A Review**, *Indo Am. J. P. Sci*, 2017; 4(09).

INTRODUCTION:

According to published statistics by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer is the second leading cause of death after cardiovascular diseases throughout the world. The American Cancer Society announced in its latest report that out of every eight women, one is diagnosed with breast cancer (1). The rate of cancer in developed countries is increasing from 1 to 0.2% and in developing countries about 0.5% annually. According to a report by the World Health Organization in 2011, cancer in Iran was reported to be 12% widespread and was recognized as the third most common cause of death (2). Gastric cancer, breast cancer, and colorectal cancer are the three common cancers in Iran respectively. Breast cancer is the first place cancer widespread among women (3). The average age of breast cancer diagnosis in the Western countries is 56 years and in Iran 45 years. New developments in the patients care with breast cancer have increased the overall survival rate of the patients in recent years. This increase in survival has doubled the importance of predictive factors of local recurrence and distant metastases of the disease (4). In addition, it should be noted that the progression or regression of some diseases are not constant over time, as in the stages of recovery or worsening of the disease, the occurrence of some consequences changes the course of the disease, and the disease progress declines and this risk begins to decrease in the 2-5 years after treatment, which make the recovery process speed (5).

METHODS:

In this review article, the databases Medline, Cochrane, Science Direct, and Google Scholar were thoroughly searched to identify the Preventing Breast cancer. In this review, the papers published until early January 2017 that were conducted to study the relationship between the Preventing Breast cancer were selected.

RESULTS:

When a small tumor, breast cancer typically does not cause any symptoms. Therefore, it is important that women have the screening guidelines for determining breast cancer at initial stages (6). When breast cancer grows to the extent that can be felt, the most common physical symptom is a painless mass. Sometimes cancer can spread to lymph nodes under the arm and makes a lump. Other less common symptoms include painful or heavy breast, nipple abnormalities in the form of spontaneous discharge, itching and scaly nipples, pointing inwards, feeling tender, the skin looking orange peel, and any other apparent new changes like wound, blushing, prominent blood vessels,

pointing inward, and extension in the skin or nipple (7). All women should be familiar with the appearance of their breasts and should be able to watch their breasts in front of the mirror and examine them and report any changes to their doctors immediately. However, American Cancer Association no longer recommends doing monthly BSE, and specialists believe that BSE has the minimum effect in diagnosing breast cancer. Breast masses are not necessarily abnormal, and for women who have menstrual cycle, breast masses appear and disappear (8).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

In women without symptoms in their 20s and 30s, it is suggested that breast examination be part of an appropriate health examination that is done at least once every three years. For women aging 40 and above, annual CBE can be an important complement to mammography, because a small percentage of cancer cases may not be diagnosed through mammography (9). In CBE, doctors use their finger pads to gently feel the breast and examine the breast for texture, the location of each mass, and whether the mass sticks to the skin or to the deeper tissue, and also the underarm areas (10). A study showed that CBE and mammography together have a greater sensitivity than mammography alone. However, it has higher false positives, too. Mammography often diagnoses breast cancers without symptoms in women, but not all types of them (11). For women with less breast tissue, new technologies like digital mammography are more sensitive and have been a promising development for women with dense breast tissue. FDA (Food and Drug Administration) has recently approved using several ultrasound technologies in addition to standard mammography for women with dense breast tissue (11). Mammography is a process with low dosage of X ray in which the danger of the X ray is minimum (12). This technology makes it possible to see the internal structures of the breast. American Cancer Association suggests that women reaching the age of 40 have an annual mammography. Initial prevention in the form of changes in lifestyle, avoiding risk factors, and education and informing people through mass media like radio, TV, and newspapers in order to increase people's awareness of methods of breast cancer screening is suggested.

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